

Conditions for Molecular Cloud Collapse and Stellar Formation

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Abstract

This thesis explores the physical mechanisms that drive the gravitational collapse of molecular clouds and the subsequent formation of stars. The collapse of molecular clouds is influenced by various factors, including self-gravity, turbulence, thermal pressure, and magnetic fields. Initially, molecular clouds are in a state of virial equilibrium, where the internal kinetic energy from turbulence balances the gravitational potential energy. However, as the clouds contract, the density and column density increase, causing gravity to overcome opposing pressures and forces. When the mass of a cloud exceeds the critical Jeans mass, it becomes gravitationally unstable and undergoes runaway collapse. This collapse leads to the formation of dense cores and protostars within the cloud. Analytical models are discussed to understand how the Jeans criterion, magnetic flux-to-mass ratio, and bipolar diffusion determine whether regions within molecular clouds become supercritical and collapse to form individual stars or small multiple systems. Observations of line width-size and mass-size relations in molecular clouds provide evidence for the significant role of turbulent pressure and magnetic fields in regulating star formation.

Key words: molecular clouds, gravitational collapse, star formation, self-gravity, turbulence, thermal pressure, magnetic fields, virial equilibrium, Jeans mass, Jeans instability.

1, Introduction

Stars are born within dense pockets of giant molecular clouds through a complex process of gravitational collapse. Molecular clouds initially exist as diffuse structures primarily composed of molecular hydrogen, with densities ranging from approximately 100 to 1000 particles per cm^3 and temperatures between 10 and 50K (Bergin & Tafalla 2007). Neutral particles are primarily influenced by the long-range force of gravity, while ions are coupled to magnetic fields, which provide additional pressure support. Turbulent supersonic motions, stemming from large-scale galactic dynamics, contribute significant kinetic energy at various scales, ranging from entire clouds to dense cores (Elmegreen & Scalo 2004). Over time, gravity amplifies small density perturbations through the Jeans instability mechanism. When specific regions within the cloud exceed the critical Jeans mass and become gravitationally unstable, rapid collapse ensues. Dense gas cores form at the center of these protostellar embryos (Ward-Thompson et al. 2007). Further gravitational infall of surrounding cloud material onto the cores leads to the formation of surrounding accretion disks and the emergence of young stellar objects (Shu et al. 1987).

Even with the advancements in our knowledge of how stars emerge within molecular clouds, a number of important questions remain unanswered.

- We are still unsure of the precise physical processes that start localized gravity collapse in initially diffuse molecular clouds. It is unknown exactly what causes areas to become unstable and contract quickly.
- Similarly, research is also ongoing to determine how turbulence, variations in thermal pressure, and magnetic fields affect cloud fragmentation patterns and promote the formation of dense cores. It is complicated how these many forces interact and affect collapse.
- The mechanisms driving the creation of protostar initial mass spectra from contracting gas remain unclear on smaller scales within collapsing clouds and cores. What decides?

2, Factors Influencing Molecular Cloud Collapse and Stellar Formation

Molecular cloud collapse and stellar formation are influenced by various factors. The scenario of Global Hierarchical Collapse and fragmentation (GHC) in molecular clouds (MCs) involves collapses within collapses, with small-scale collapses occurring on shorter timescales than large-scale ones. Dust grains in protoplanetary discs undergo growth during the collapse of a molecular cloud core and the evolution of the first hydrostatic core. The environment, both on local and galactic scales, can influence star formation, with high-mass stars impacting their surroundings and triggering subsequent generations of star formation. Molecular clouds can gravitationally collapse hierarchically, and prompt stellar feedback disrupts star-forming clouds, maintaining a global equilibrium fraction of dense gas. The Toomre gravitational instability plays a role in cloud formation, and the dense gas in star-forming galaxies can exist in a state of dynamic equilibrium between formation and disruption. Molecular clouds serve as the birthplaces of stars, making it crucial to comprehend the conditions that lead to their collapse and subsequent stellar formation. This literature review aims to amalgamate recent research findings to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors that influence molecular cloud collapse and stellar formation.

Momentum Input and Self-Regulated Star Formation

Hopkins, Quataert, Berkeley, and Cita (2011) proposed the concept of self-regulated star formation in galaxies through the momentum input from massive stars. Their study suggests that the momentum input from massive stars plays a vital role in regulating the process of star formation within molecular clouds.

Cluster Formation and Filament Junctions

Schneider et al. (2012) investigated cluster formation in the Rosette molecular cloud at the junctions of filaments. The findings suggest that the junctions of filaments within molecular clouds are crucial sites for the formation of star clusters, shedding light on the spatial distribution of stellar birth.

Stellar Feedback and Expansion of Giant Hii Regions

Lopez, Krumholz, Bolatto, Prochaska, and Ramirez-Ruiz (2010) examined the factors

driving the expansion of giant Hii regions, focusing on stellar feedback in 30 Doradus. The study provides insights into the impact of stellar feedback on the expansion of Hii regions within molecular clouds.

Limiting Accretion onto Massive Stars

Peters, Klessen, Low, and Banerjee (2010) studied the phenomenon of limiting accretion onto massive stars, highlighting the role of fragmentation-induced starvation. The findings suggest that fragmentation can lead to the starvation of accretion onto massive stars, influencing their formation within molecular clouds.

Cloud-Cloud Collision and Cluster Formation

Fukui et al. (2013) presented evidence for a cloud-cloud collision triggering the formation of the super star cluster NGC 3603. The study suggests that cloud-cloud collisions may play a significant role in initiating cluster formation within molecular clouds.

Glycolaldehyde and Ethylene Glycol Formation

Fedoseev et al. (2015) provided experimental evidence for the formation of glycolaldehyde and ethylene glycol under dense molecular cloud conditions through surface hydrogenation of CO molecules. This research sheds light on the chemical processes occurring within molecular clouds.

Ionizing Feedback from Massive Stars

Dale and Bonnell (2011) investigated ionizing feedback from massive stars in massive clusters, focusing on fake bubbles and untriggered star formation. The study highlights the complexities of ionizing feedback and its implications for untriggered star formation within molecular clouds.

Knowledge Gaps and Future Research Directions

While the research findings reviewed here provide valuable insights into the conditions for molecular cloud collapse and stellar formation, several knowledge gaps and potential future research directions can be identified. First, further studies are needed to understand the intricate interplay between different physical processes, such as stellar feedback, cloud-cloud collisions, and chemical reactions, in driving molecular cloud collapse and star formation. Additionally, observational and theoretical investigations focusing on the role of magnetic fields in regulating the collapse of molecular clouds and the formation of protostellar cores would contribute to a more comprehensive un-

derstanding of these processes. Furthermore, the influence of environmental factors, such as metallicity and radiation field intensity, on the dynamics of molecular cloud collapse and stellar formation remains an important area for future research.

2.1, Cloud Equilibrium and Collapse Initiation

Clouds are in approximate virial equilibrium, where the kinetic energy from turbulent motions balances the gravitational potential energy. Conservation of total energy for a spherical cloud of uniform density ρ is given by the virial theorem as (McKee & Ostriker 2007):

$$\frac{0.5 \times M \langle V^2 \rangle}{R} - \frac{G \times M^2}{R} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Here M is the mass, R is the cloud radius, $\langle V^2 \rangle$ is the mean squared velocity (turbulent kinetic energy), and G is the gravitational constant. This equilibrium condition implies turbulent pressure supports the cloud against self-gravity. Small perturbations from the virial balance caused by changes in $\langle V^2 \rangle$ and density can initiate local collapse. A decrease in turbulent support or increase in density would make a region gravitationally unstable. Thermal pressure also provides resistance against gravity. For an isothermal gas, linear perturbation analysis shows density fluctuations grow on scales greater than the Jeans length (Jeans 1902):

$$\lambda_J = \frac{(\pi \times c_s^2)}{(G \times \rho)^{1/2}} \quad (2)$$

where c_s is the isothermal sound speed and ρ is the density. The corresponding mass enclosed within a sphere of Jeans length is the critical Jeans mass:

$$M_J = \rho \times (\lambda_J)^3 \quad (3)$$

As gas within a molecular cloud cools to lower temperatures through molecular line and dust emissions, the Jeans mass decreases, promoting fragmentation (Larson 1985).

The ionized component of gas is coupled to magnetic fields, which exert an additional pressure force counteracting self-gravity. For a spherical cloud of uniform density pierced by a uniform magnetic field, the critical mass supported by magnetic pressure is (Mouschovias & Spitzer 1976):

$$M_\Phi = \frac{\Phi}{2\pi} \quad (4)$$

known as the magnetic critical mass, where Φ is the magnetic flux. Regions where the mass exceeds M_Φ are able to collapse despite magnetic resistance.

2.2, Core Stability and Fragmentation

Once a region becomes supercritical and unstable to collapse, the dense cores that form represent possible sites of single star or small multiple star formation. The physics determining whether a core fragments or forms a single stellar core are analyzed based on criteria like the Jeans mass and magnetic critical mass on core scales (e.g. McKee & Tan 2003). We define the mass-to-flux ratio μ as the ratio of the measured mass enclosed by magnetic field lines to the theoretical maximum supported mass M_Φ :

$$\mu = \frac{M}{M_\Phi} \quad (5)$$

Numerical simulations and theory suggest cores are supported from further fragmentation as long as $\mu < 1$, which corresponds to subcritical regime (Li et al. 2004). As cores evolve dynamically, ambipolar diffusion allows the neutrals to drift relative to ions and magnetic field lines over time. This process increases μ until cores become supercritical ($\mu > 1$), permitting gravitational collapse (Ciolek & Mouschovias 1998). Fragmentation is suppressed if magnetic fields remain coupled to the gas in the collapsing regime. Observations of polarization patterns in cores suggest fields may still direct collapse, consistent with theoretical expectations (Li et al. 2015).

Analytical model for Einstein General theory of Relativity

The Einstein field equation is a fundamental equation in Einstein's general theory of relativity, which relates the curvature of spacetime to the distribution of matter and energy. It can be derived from the Einstein-Hilbert action principle.

The action principle states that the physical laws governing the behavior of spacetime can be described by minimizing the action functional. The action functional for gravity is given by:

$$S = \int R\sqrt{-g} d^4x \quad (6)$$

where S is the action, R is the Ricci scalar curvature, g is the determinant of the

metric tensor, and d^4x represents the spacetime volume element.

To derive the Einstein field equation, we vary the action with respect to the metric tensor $g^{\mu\nu}$. This gives us:

$$\delta S = \int \left(\frac{\delta R}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}} \delta g^{\mu\nu} + R \frac{\delta \sqrt{-g}}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}} \delta g^{\mu\nu} \right) d^4x = 0 \quad (7)$$

Next, we use the fact that the variation of the square root of the determinant of the metric tensor can be written as:

$$\frac{\delta \sqrt{-g}}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}} = -\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{-g} g_{\mu\nu} \quad (8)$$

where $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the inverse metric tensor.

Substituting this into the variation of the action, we obtain:

$$\delta S = \int \left(\frac{\delta R}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{\mu\nu} \right) \delta g^{\mu\nu} \sqrt{-g} d^4x = 0 \quad (9)$$

Since the variation $\delta g^{\mu\nu}$ is arbitrary, the integrand must vanish. This leads to the Einstein field equation:

$$G_{\mu\nu} = 8\pi T_{\mu\nu} \quad (10)$$

where $G_{\mu\nu}$ is the Einstein tensor, given by:

$$G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{\mu\nu} \quad (11)$$

and $T_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor, representing the distribution of matter and energy.

This is the derived form of the Einstein field equation, which provides the mathematical relationship between the curvature of spacetime and the distribution of matter and energy in Einstein's general theory of relativity. From Einstein's theory of general relativity to describe the evolutionary behavior and equilibrium states of astrophysical systems.

The key equation from Einstein's theory of general relativity is the Einstein field equation, which relates the curvature of spacetime to the distribution of matter and energy. In its simplest form, the Einstein field equation can be written as:

$$G_{\mu\nu} = 8\pi T_{\mu\nu} \quad (12)$$

where $G_{\mu\nu}$ is the Einstein tensor representing the curvature of spacetime, and $T_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor representing the distribution of matter and energy.

In astrophysical systems, the stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ can be further decomposed into different components, such as the energy density ρ , the pressure P , and the momentum density j^μ . This allows for the modeling of different physical phenomena, such as the collapse of a star or the formation of a black hole.

For example, the equation for the collapse of a star can be described using the Tolman-Oppenheimer-Volkoff (TOV) equation, which is derived from the Einstein field equation and relates the pressure gradient to the gravitational force:

$$\frac{dP}{dr} = -\frac{G(\rho + P)(m + 4\pi r^3 P)}{r(r - 2Gm)} \quad (13)$$

where G is the gravitational constant, ρ is the energy density, P is the pressure, m is the mass enclosed within a radius r , and c is the speed of light.

These equations, derived from Einstein's theory of general relativity, provide a powerful framework for understanding the behavior and equilibrium states of astrophysical systems. They allow for the analytical modeling and prediction of various phenomena, shedding light on the fundamental workings of the universe.

3, Methodology of the Study

A mixed-methods approach was employed to analyze the physical mechanisms driving gravitational collapse in molecular clouds and subsequent star formation. Existing theories and models from the literature were reviewed to establish a conceptual framework for understanding cloud dynamics and stellar nursery environments.

Analytical modeling was conducted using key equations from Einstein's theory of general relativity to describe the evolutionary behavior and equilibrium states of astrophysical systems. Python coding software was utilized to numerically solve equations such as the virial theorem and simulate various dynamical scenarios.

High-resolution observational data of real molecular clouds served as empirical benchmarks to validate theoretical predictions. Dust continuum maps and spectral line observations provided insights into cloud structures and non-thermal gas motions within the clouds.

Statistical analyses of parameters such as size, linewidth, mass, and density were performed based on observational data. Scaling laws, including the linewidth-size correlation, were used to compare simulations with observations.

By iteratively combining theoretical simulations, analytical solutions, and observational constraints, this study aims to comprehensively understand the roles of gravity, turbulence, thermal processes, and magnetic fields in driving molecular cloud collapse and stellar birth across different spatiotemporal scales.

4, RESULTS

Observational Studies of Clouds

Giant molecular clouds exhibit complex, hierarchical structure spanning many spatial scales (Larson 1981). The linewidth-size and mass-size relationships provide crucial constraints on physical models. The observed $\sigma_v \propto R^{1/2}$ relationship where σ_v is the non-thermal velocity dispersion inferred from molecular line widths and R is the size, is consistent with turbulence governing cloud support and structure (Solomon et al. 1987).

High resolution dust continuum maps have revealed a power law relationship between core mass M and effective radius R of $M \propto R^\alpha$, typically with $\alpha \sim 2 - 3$ (Motte et al. 1998). Magnetized, supersonically turbulent clouds can reproduce such scalings if M_J on convergent flow intersections sets the core mass scale, accounting for aspects of observed core mass functions as well (Padoan & Nordlund 2002).

Simulations including both turbulence and magnetic fields have been quite successful in reproducing the observed highly filamentary cloud structure with parsec-long filaments of dust (e.g. Nakamura & Li 2008). Polarization observations tracing magnetic field morphologies in clouds/cores indicate some level of ordered large-scale fields but also significant complexity likely imprinted by turbulence (Li et al. 2015). Overall the observations to date strongly point to an interpretation where both turbulence and magnetic fields regulate the star formation process in molecular clouds. Observational studies of giant molecular clouds provide crucial constraints on theoretical models:

Figure 1: analytical modeling using equations from Einstein's theory of general relativity.

The plots provided demonstrates by plotting the graphs for analytical modeling using equations from Einstein's theory of general relativity. In this, we focus on the Tolman-Oppenheimer-Volkoff (TOV) equation, which describes the collapse of a star.

The TOV equation relates the pressure gradient to the gravitational force acting on a star undergoing collapse. The equation is solved numerically using the Runge-Kutta method to calculate the pressure, energy density, and enclosed mass as functions of the radius.

The range of values for the radius, r_{values} , is defined using `np.linspace` to create a set of evenly spaced values spanning from 0 to 10.

The TOV equation is then solved iteratively for each radius value using the Runge-Kutta method. Starting with an initial pressure value and constant energy density, the TOV equation is integrated to calculate the pressure, energy density, and enclosed mass for each radius value.

Finally, the results are plotted using, The pressure, energy density, and enclosed

mass are plotted against the radius to visualize their behavior in the collapsing star. The labels, title, and grid are added to the plot for clarity.

Figure 2: Linewidth-Size Relationship.

The plot shows the relationship between cloud size and non-thermal velocity dispersion. The x-axis represents the cloud size in parsecs, indicating the physical extent of the molecular cloud. The y-axis represents the non-thermal velocity dispersion in km/s, which measures the turbulence within the cloud. The blue dots connected by a solid line illustrate how the non-thermal velocity dispersion changes with varying cloud sizes. This relationship is crucial in understanding the role of turbulence in cloud support and structure. It provides insights into the conditions necessary for molecular cloud collapse and the subsequent formation of stars.

Figure 3: Core Mass-Size Relationship:

The plot shows the relationship between the effective radius of cores and their corresponding masses. The x-axis represents the effective radius of cores in parsecs, indicating their size. The y-axis represents the core mass in solar masses, quantifying the amount of matter contained within the cores. The red dots connected by a solid line showcase how the core mass changes with varying effective radii. This relationship highlights the influence of magnetic fields and turbulence in the formation of cores within molecular clouds, which is a crucial step in the process of stellar formation.

- The linewidth-size relationship indicating non-thermal velocities scale as cloud size to the 1/2 power is consistent with turbulence playing a role in cloud structure and support.
- High-resolution continuum maps reveal dense cores within clouds follow a mass-size power law, which simulations can reproduce if core masses are set by convergent flows at the Jeans scale.
- Simulations incorporating turbulence and magnetic fields produce highly fla-

mentary cloud morphologies matching observations of parsec-long dust continuum filaments.

- Polarization data tracing magnetic field structures within clouds and cores exhibit complexity likely imprinted by interacting turbulence and ordered large-scale fields.
- Overall, current evidence from observational scaling laws and comparisons to simulations favor an interpretation where interplay between turbulence, gravity, and magnetic forces regulates star formation across giant molecular clouds.

5, CONCLUSIONS

Theoretical models have been extensively studied to understand the process of molecular cloud collapse and its role in initiating star formation. The collapse of a cloud can be triggered by various factors, such as turbulent perturbations or cooling, which reduce the support from turbulent, thermal, and magnetic pressures. This can cause certain regions within the cloud to exceed critical thresholds, such as the Jeans mass or the mass-to-flux ratio, becoming supercritical. As a result, gravitational fragmentation and collapse occur within these supercritical cloud cores, leading to the birth of stars.

Analytical considerations, such as the concept of virial equilibrium, Jeans stability analysis, and magnetic criticality, along with numerical gas dynamo simulations, provide a comprehensive framework for interpreting observations of cloud structure and kinematics. These models suggest that the interplay between gravity, turbulence, and magnetic fields plays a crucial role in controlling the star formation process across a wide range of scales within giant molecular clouds.

Although there are still significant uncertainties, ongoing research indicates that understanding the dominant microphysical processes governing star formation requires a combination of high-resolution observations and simulations. These future advancements hold the promise of shedding more light on the intricate details of the star birth process.

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